

ODISSEI User Policy

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1. Introduction

ODISSEI is the Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations (www.odissei-data.nl). It consists of [Member Organisations](#) that pay an annual membership fee. ODISSEI uses the revenue generated through the membership fees and through 3rd party financing to provide services to its Member Organisations. In order to access these services, an individual must be employed by an ODISSEI Member Organisation. This document sets out the 'Terms of Participation' for individuals at a Member Organisation who wish to use an ODISSEI Service.

The [ODISSEI Management Board](#) is responsible for the development and maintenance of these terms of participation. It is the responsibility of the [ODISSEI Coordination Team](#) (info@odissei-data.nl) to ensure that these terms of participation are visible, enabled and enacted.

ODISSEI is a federated infrastructure which provides a single operational framework for multiple **ODISSEI Service Providers** to support social scientists. These Service Providers include but are not limited to Statistics Netherlands (CBS), SURF, Centerdata, Netherlands eScience Center, and DANS. Service Providers have their own independent terms of use and operational policies in addition to those presented here. All ODISSEI Service Providers are also Member Organisations themselves. If there is a conflict between the policies of the Service Provider and ODISSEI with respect to research conducted as part of ODISSEI, it is the responsibility of the Service Provider to make the ODISSEI Coordination Team aware of this conflict. It is the responsibility of the ODISSEI Coordination Team to evaluate the conflict and defer to the ODISSEI Management Board where necessary. Data made available by ODISSEI Service Providers such as CBS Microdata, the LISS panel or the data collections that are supported by ODISSEI (such as SHARE, GGP, EVS, NKO, etc.) need to be FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable). This is the responsibility of the Service Provider.

An **ODISSEI User** is someone who engages with a Service Provider under the framework of ODISSEI. This means that a Service Provider is providing a service that is conditional on the user being an employee at an ODISSEI member organisation. For example, a recipient of a Microdata Access Grant, Microdata Access Discount, a LISS grant, a SoDa project, an ODISSEI eScience project or any other ODISSEI service.

An ODISSEI User can either process the data of an ODISSEI Service Provider or use an ODISSEI service to process their own data. In this document, such data that is used in conjunction with an ODISSEI service by an ODISSEI User is referred to as '**User Data**', regardless of whether this is data provided by an ODISSEI Service Provider and processed by the User or it is data brought into ODISSEI by the user and then processed. Such data must be FAIR and is subject to these terms of participation. Failure to do so may curtail their rights to use ODISSEI Services.

In addition to User Data, this User Policy also applies to **Metadata**, or the description of the User Data, and **Research software or Code**, namely "the set of operations that describe the steps taken to collect

and manipulate raw data into an end result, written in an informatic language such as Python, R, STATA or many others¹.

¹ See also: De Boer, Lieke, Cammarata, Emilio, Martinez Ortiz, Carlos, and Maineri, Angelica. "FAIR Software for the Social Sciences". Zenodo, June 9, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8020325>.

2. Legal and Ethical Requirements

Legal Requirements

ODISSEI is not a data controller. This means that ODISSEI does not hold or own research data. ODISSEI Users or Service Providers always remain the controller of their data. All User Data remains with its respective owner and no transfer of Intellectual Property occurs, unless explicitly stated otherwise.

Most of the User Data will contain personal data or even sensitive personal data and therefore falls under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)². Sensitive personal data in ODISSEI should be processed under [Article 9\(2\(J\)\)](#) of the GDPR (EU 2016/679). These are 'Research Grounds' for the processing of personal data. This means that processing must be in the public interest, or for scientific, research or statistical purposes. To ensure this is observed, ODISSEI and all ODISSEI Users shall act in accordance with [Article 89\(1\)](#) of the GDPR:

Processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organizational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimization. Those measures may include pseudonymization provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.

Data processed on 'Research Grounds'³ must be pseudonymized or anonymized where possible, and minimized to the level necessary for research purposes. Users must also ensure that research code and metadata do not lead to unwanted disclosure of individuals, companies and institutions, just as is the case with data Access to and use of User Data will only be for research purposes. It is the responsibility of an ODISSEI Service Provider to ensure that adequate security and technical measures shall be put in place to ensure compliance with [Article 89\(1\)](#) and the responsibility of ODISSEI Users to only process data for research purposes. ODISSEI Users should report to the ODISSEI Coordination Team and respective Service Provider if they perceive security or technical measures to be inadequate.

The use of ODISSEI services shall not be for commercial purposes or for purposes other than those outlined in Article 89(1) of the GDPR. Data processing should be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.

² In order for the GDPR not to apply, the data must be fully anonymized and it must be impossible to identify individual subjects within the data.

³ Research is defined by Recital 159 of the GDPR, and "should be interpreted in a broad manner including for example technological development and demonstration, fundamental research, applied research and privately funded research"

Ethical Requirements

ODISSEI Users must be registered employees at one of these [ODISSEI member organisations](#). Ethical approval needs to be in place in cases where the User wants to collect, analyse, store or share personal data using the ODISSEI infrastructure. Ethical approval should be obtained at the respective member organisation and should be in line with the institutional requirements of the organization. This ethical approval should critically evaluate participant information sheets and consent procedures where applicable. Cases that are particularly complex or sensitive, or those presenting a specific conflict of interest can be referred to the ODISSEI Data Protection Office (dpo@odissei-data.nl) under the discretion of the relevant user's institution.

Processing User Data may require further ethical considerations as stipulated by the data controller, in instances where this is not the data user. Where applicable, this will be clearly indicated and completed in a timely manner by the data controller.

In case the User wants to collect, analyse, store or share their own data, we strongly advise to make a Data Management Plan (DMP), following a suitable standardized DMP template, for instance from NWO or from the User's own institution, and describe the data and procedures in as much detail as possible. This is often part of the ethical approval in any case. For software developed by the User, we recommend having a Software Management Plan (SMP).⁴ Support to fill in a DMP is usually available via the data steward at the user's institution; if no local support is available, please feel free to contact the ODISSEI FAIR Support team (fairsupport@odissei-data.nl) for any query.

⁴ For guidance on this, please see the "[Practical guide to Software Management Plans](#)", and the [SMP decision tree](#).

3. FAIR Research

An open data infrastructure is one that increases the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of data and other research objects (e.g. software, outputs). ODISSEI Users are required to ensure User Data and other research objects are FAIR. The general FAIR principles are displayed in Appendix A. In order to ensure that all User Data aligns with the FAIR principles, the following specific ODISSEI guidelines apply:

Findable

- User Data must be accompanied with appropriate and detailed metadata and documentation that accurately describes the dataset and provides all relevant information including usage rights, licenses and associated datasets.
- User Data should be documented using existing international metadata standards. If unsure of the appropriate standard, the ODISSEI User should consult with the ODISSEI FAIR support team (fairsupport@odissei-data.nl).
- Metadata must be publicly available under a CC0 license.
- Metadata should be provided in English and, where relevant, Dutch information should be added.
- Research code must be accompanied with appropriate and detailed metadata and documentation that accurately describe the steps undertaken to process and analyse the data.
- Research code working on LISS panel data and/or CBS microdata should be made findable via the [ODISSEI Code Library](#).
- Non peer-reviewed research outputs such as presentations or reports should be published in the [ODISSEI Zenodo Community](#) (see more on the [ODISSEI website](#)), especially if they have been presented at an ODISSEI-related event (e.g. ODISSEI Annual Conference, ODISSEI lunch lecture).

Accessible

- User Data should be deposited in a Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR)⁵, like the [DANS Data Station SSH](#), and allocated a Persistent Identifier (PID) within 6 months of a research project being completed. Exceptions based on the sensitivity of the data (see more in section 5) should be discussed with the ODISSEI FAIR support team (fairsupport@odissei-data.nl).
- A dataset's access procedures must be published as part of its metadata. If access to data is restricted, a Data Access Protocol should be established where procedures are described. The recommended template is available at [this link](#). These procedures should be clear, comprehensive and transparent. Generic formulations such as "data available upon reasonable request" are not acceptable. Access to the data should be sustainable in so much as they are not dependent on the consent of a specific individual.

⁵ The concept of Trustworthy Digital Repositories is explained in more detail in this paper: Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. *et al.* The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* 7, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

- It is not permissible to restrict access to User Data due to a conflict or overlap with existing research projects. Nor is it permissible to require co-authorship of resulting scientific papers as a condition of access.

Interoperable

- User Data should use international standards and best practices regarding interoperability (e.g. on formats and vocabularies) where possible.
- User Data should be stored in open and sustainable formats. For a list of formats that can be considered sustainable see for instance the [recommendations by DANS](#).
- User (Meta)data should make use of known structured vocabularies where possible. [A list of recommendations](#) for ontologies and controlled vocabularies is maintained by the ODISSEI community.
- User Data should include metadata that is stored in a machine-readable format, e.g. by archiving and publishing the User Data in your local repository or a domain-specific repository like the [DANS Data Station SSH](#).

Reusable

- User Data should be published following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” (see also section 5).
- When creating a Data Management Plan (DMP), ODISSEI Users should follow a suitable standardized DMP template, for instance from [NWO](#) or from the User's own institution, and describe the data and procedures in as much detail as possible.
- Research Software or Code used to produce, enhance or adapt the User Data should be made available alongside the User Data where possible via a suitable code repository (e.g., Open Science Framework - OSF, Zenodo, Research Software Directory, etc..). Efforts should be made to enhance the FAIRness of the code, e.g. by following the recommendations for FAIR-software (www.fair-software.nl)⁶. [A short practical guide for preparing and sharing your analysis code](#) is available on the ODISSEI website.
- Data and Software/Code must be accurately cited in scientific research with reference to the dataset's and research software's Persistent Identifier (PID).
- The licence of the data should be specified and preferably a standardized license is chosen, (see for instance the [licences](#) offered by the [DANS Data Station SSH](#):). For research software, we recommend assigning the open source Apache2 licence.

⁶ While Git is recommended for version control, whenever a specific version of the code is associated with a research output (e.g. a publication), it is recommended to also publish the code (or the git repository) in a general-purpose repository which provides persistent identifiers, such as the Research Software Directory, Zenodo or Open Science Framework (OSF).

4. FACT Users

ODISSEI Users must adhere to the [Netherlands code of conduct for research integrity](#). This code emphasizes honesty, scrupulousness, transparency, independence and responsibility. ODISSEI Users are also required to abide by the FACT principles⁷ which emphasize Fairness, Accuracy, Confidentiality and Transparency. FACT principles compliment FAIR principles by providing a research code of conduct for data intensive research.

Fair

- ODISSEI Users are responsible for communicating data and analytical methods in a fair and balanced manner.
- ODISSEI Users will avoid unfair conclusions without due consideration for the manner in which the data was collected, processed and analyzed.
- ODISSEI Users must critically assess analytical outputs and interpret them in a fair and balanced way and present all analytical outputs alongside the limitations of the data and methods used.

Accurate

- ODISSEI Users must strive for accuracy throughout the research lifecycle to avoid misleading conclusions.
- ODISSEI Users are responsible for the communication, not only of results, but the accuracy of such results and the degree of accuracy of any analysis.
- The communication of accuracy is not dependent on the audience to which the results are being communicated.

Confidential

- ODISSEI Users are required to report any breach of confidentiality or data subjects' rights to the ODISSEI Coordination Team immediately.
- ODISSEI Users must refrain from undertaking analysis which disclose the identity of a specific individual or organization.
- ODISSEI Users are responsible for communicating with data subjects in a clear and accessible way with regards to the risks associated with participating in a study and their rights when doing so.

Transparent

- ODISSEI Users must make all data processing code associated with published scientific outputs available under an open license.

⁷ van der Aalst, W.M.P, Bichler, M. & Heinzl, A. Responsible Data Science. Bus Inf Syst Eng 59, 311–313 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-017-0487-z>.

- ODISSEI Users are responsible for accurately documenting all generated data and associated code.
- ODISSEI Users are required to enable and facilitate replication of analysis wherever possible.
- ODISSEI users must acknowledge the use of ODISSEI services in any publication resulting from data processed on ODISSEI infrastructure, for example using the text below or equivalent: *"This research was conducted in whole or in part using ODISSEI, the Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations (<https://ror.org/03m8v6t10>)"*

5. Open Science

ODISSEI subscribes to the principle of 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'.

All ODISSEI users must follow the [open access policy of NWO](#) for publications originating from the research projects.

As mentioned above in the section on FAIR Research, User Data should be archived in a Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR, like the [DANS Data Station SSH](#)) and where possible be shared with an open license. Exceptions can be made when data contains sensitive information or (sensitive) personal data. Depending on the sensitivity, User Data can be published in a TDR under restricted access or - in cases where data is extremely sensitive - the use of controlled environments (e.g. SANE) can be required. The User should strive to make as much information and User Data available for reuse as possible. This can for instance include the publication of de-identified data, publishing parts of a dataset that does not contain sensitive information, or the creation of synthetic data. In all cases, metadata and documentation of all User Data needs to be made available under an open CC0-license. In addition, production code should be made openly available and the guidelines for FAIR software and code should be followed (www.fair-software.nl).

In cases where data cannot be openly shared this should be discussed with the ODISSEI FAIR support team (fairsupport@odissei-data.nl). Special dispensation to charge for access to User Data must be obtained from the ODISSEI Management Board.

Appendix A – FAIR Principles⁸

FAIR principles:⁹

F	FINDABLE
F1	(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier
F2	data are described with rich metadata
F3	(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource (able to google data-objects)
F4	metadata specify the data identifier
A	ACCESSIBLE
A1	(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol
A1.1	the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
A1.2	the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
A2	metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available
I	INTEROPERABLE
I1	(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
I2	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
I3	(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
R	REUSABLE
R1	(meta)data have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
R1.1	(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
R1.2	(meta)data are associated with their provenance
R1.3	(meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

⁸ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

FAIR principles for Research Software.¹⁰

F	Software, and its associated metadata, is easy for both humans and machines to find.
F1	F1. Software is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier. F1.1. Components of the software representing levels of granularity are assigned distinct identifiers. F1.2. Different versions of the software are assigned distinct identifiers.
F2	F2. Software is described with rich metadata.
F3	F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the software they describe.
F4	F4. Metadata are FAIR, searchable and indexable.
A	Software, and its metadata, is retrievable via standardised protocols.
A1	A1. Software is retrievable by its identifier using a standardised communications protocol. A1.1. The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable. A1.2. The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
A2	A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the software is no longer available.
I	I: Software interoperates with other software by exchanging data and/or metadata, and/or through interaction via application programming interfaces (APIs), described through standards.
I1	I1. Software reads, writes and exchanges data in a way that meets domain-relevant community standards.
I2	I2. Software includes qualified references to other objects.
R	R: Software is both usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other software).
R1	R1. Software is described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. R1.1. Software is given a clear and accessible license. R1.2. Software is associated with detailed provenance.
R2	R2. Software includes qualified references to other software..
R3	R3. Software meets domain-relevant community standards.

¹⁰ Barker, M., Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S. et al. Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. Sci Data 9, 622 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

Appendix B – Glossary

Terms	Explanations
CBS	Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (Statistics Netherlands)
Data controller	The instance that determines the purposes for which and the means by which personal data is processed. This is typically a formal legal entity that is responsible for the maintenance and use of the data. A data controller can grant access and processing rights to a data processor.
Data processor	The instance that processes personal data only on behalf of the controller. This can be an organization or an individual researcher.
EVS	European Values Study
FACT	Fair, Accurate, Confidential, and Transparent data analysis.
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data
GGP	Generations and Gender Programme
ISO	International Standardization Organization
LISS	Longitudinal Internet studies for the Social Sciences
NKO	Nationaal Kiezersonderzoek (Dutch National Election Study)
ODISSEI	The Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations, see www.odissei-data.nl .
ODISSEI Coordination Team	The team responsible for day-to-day operations of ODISSEI, located at Erasmus University Rotterdam (info@odissei-data.nl).
ODISSEI Data Protection Office	The part of the ODISSEI Coordination Team that deals with data protection (dpo@odissei-data.nl).
ODISSEI Infrastructure	The conjunction of all facilities operated by ODISSEI Service Providers partners that are developed using ODISSEI funding
ODISSEI Management Board	The ODISSEI board that supervises day-to-day operations.
ODISSEI Member Organisation	Organisations that pay an annual contribution to ODISSEI. A list can be found on the ODISSEI site.
ODISSEI Service Provider	An ODISSEI Member Organisation operating an ODISSEI facility to provide ODISSEI Services
ODISSEI SoDa team	ODISSEI Social DATA team
ODISSEI User	Individual researchers using an ODISSEI Service
PID	A Persistent Identifier, such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) or ORCID.
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe

TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
User Data	Data and metadata that has been processed by an ODISSEI User as part of work with an ODISSEI Service Provider